

Quantifiable feasibility check of masonry assemblages composed of interlocking blocks

Elham Mousavian*, Claudia Casapulla

Department of Structures for Engineering and Architecture, University of Naples Federico II, via Forno Vecchio 36, 80134, Naples, Italy

**Corresponding author (Elham Mousavian)*

Tel./fax: +39 081 2538039

E-mail: elham.mousavian@unina.it

Abstract

This work introduces a digital tool to model single layer assemblages of interlocking blocks and quantify their structural feasibility. Interlocking blocks are rigid units that, on their faces, have locks keeping the blocks together and preventing them from sliding. The tool measures the structural infeasibility of an assemblage as a numerical value, so that the designer can adjust the geometric parameters of the assemblage and the interlocking faces to minimize the measured infeasibility. This enables the designer to remove the infeasibility according to a measured quantity and not by trial and error. To analyse the structural soundness of a model with corrugated interfaces, limit analysis has been extended to address two different sliding behaviours in two orthogonal directions. This method is comprehensively validated in this paper by comparing the thinnest feasible model of systems composed of conventional blocks existing in the literature and the models composed of interlocking blocks. Then, as the core of this work, the extended limit analysis is reformulated to develop an optimization problem to measure the structural infeasibility. The optimal solution is such that the tangential internal forces are the closest ones to the valid sliding ranges, while the model is in equilibrium and the internal normal forces are in compression. The method is validated by comparing the measured infeasibility to the structural soundness of assemblages with different geometric properties of the interlocking block faces. Finally, the performance of the developed digital tool to design single layer assemblages with arbitrary shapes is demonstrated through several examples.

Keywords: limit analysis extension; orthotropic sliding resistance; interlocking masonry blocks; measure of infeasibility; computer-aided structurally-informed design.

1. Introduction

Since the early 1990s, computers have not only assisted the designers in the structural analysis but have also suggested ways to make the initial designs to be structurally feasible. In this line, several stand-alone digital tools and plug-ins have been developed for structurally sound design of civil constructions, including masonry structures. The tools developed for masonry assemblages generally adopt structural analysis methods such as finite element analysis (FEA) for the continuous, micro and macro models [1-4], discrete element (DE) analysis [5, 6] and limit analysis [7-9].

Using these methods at the early stages of the design enables the designers to check the feasibility of the models and then tune the initial geometric parameters to reach the desired structurally sound models. However, a positive or negative answer to the feasibility query is not an efficient way for the

geometrical shape exploration. The designer should guess how the parameters must be adjusted to remove the infeasibility, and this requires a high degree of expertise. One solution to remedy the situation is to quantify and measure the amount of infeasibility. The measured infeasibility can be minimized manually or automatically through an approach which Whiting et al. [10] named “design by optimization”, in which many form-finding methods can fall [10-13].

The European SiDMACIB project, MCSA_IF No. 791235 [14], is one of the first efforts following this design approach to develop a digital tool for structurally feasible assemblages of masonry blocks with non-planar corrugated dry joints. An increasing popularity of the interlocking blocks applications has recently been registered with studies on the: in-plane and out-of-plane capacity of masonry walls with corrugated joints [15-17], out-of-plane capacity of masonry walls with osteomorphic blocks [18, 19] and cross-shaped joints [20], other than with conventional blocks [21, 22], and structural behaviour of wooden joineries with various shapes [23]. Despite this increasing interest, there are still few digital tools developed to design structurally feasible assemblages of interlocking blocks. Some studies on the computer-based design of interlocking blocks to maximize the manufacturability and assemblability, and to facilitate transportation have been reviewed by Araújo et al. [24].

The analysis applied by SiDMACIB is an extension of the limit analysis method to interlocking corrugated interfaces with orthotropic sliding behaviour [25-28]. Since the pioneering works of Heyman [7, 8], limit analysis has been recognized as an effective tool to model a masonry structure as an assemblage of rigid blocks, in which the internal forces are only distributed at the block boundaries. While the initial assumptions were based on the infinite sliding resistance [6], several studies were later carried out accommodating finite sliding resistance within the limit analysis, either governed by the Coulomb’s friction law at the dry joints or by the material shear strength at the potential crack planes inside non-rigid blocks [29-31]. Furthermore, the associative and non-associative sliding behaviour of such kinds of masonry assemblages has been taken into the consideration [32-35], but still considering the sliding resistance to be isotropic, i.e., similar in all directions.

This work presents further and novel steps in the validation of the limit analysis method proposed in [26, 28] for orthotropic interfaces. The concave contact model is adopted to abstract the stress state on the assemblage, considering that the concave and convex models are two modelling methods suitable to analyse assemblages with diverse topologies. In the concave model, the stress state at each block interface is displayed by the internal forces distributed on a number of contact points [32, 35], while in the convex one the stress state is represented by the internal forces concentrated on the centroid of the interface [36]. The proposed method assumes that sliding follows the associated flow rules (friction with dilatancy) governed by the Coulomb’s law, while solutions with non-associated flow rules can be accommodated by adopting the iterative procedure proposed by Gilbert et al. [34].

The main contribution of this paper is developing a method to quantify the structural infeasibility of such assemblages and to implement it as a plug-in in the grasshopper editor, in order to design the structurally sound single layer assemblages of interlocking blocks with corrugated interfaces.

The concept of the infeasibility measure showing how far a model is from being structurally feasible has been suggested by Whiting et al. [10]. That work measured the infeasibility caused by the existence of tensile forces in the assemblage. Similarly, in this work an efficient method to quantify the infeasibility due to the tangential forces outside the valid sliding ranges, is developed. By measuring the infeasibility, the designers can adjust the design parameters to reduce the infeasibility and finally reach a structurally feasible model.

In the following, [Section 2](#) presents the extended limit analysis to the corrugated interlocking interfaces and its validation through the analysis of three classical assemblages studied in the literature, i.e., the semi-circular arch, the hemispherical dome, and the pavilion vault. [Section 3](#)

demonstrates the reformulated limit analysis to measure the assemblage structural infeasibility. This section also includes the implementation of the method to a plug-in to design the single layer assemblages of interlocking blocks and its validation through the three examples of [Section 2](#). Three other examples with diverse geometries and loading conditions are then provided in [Section 4](#), to demonstrate the capability of the plug-in to design a wide range of structurally feasible assemblages of interlocking blocks. Finally, the conclusions are provided.

2. Limit analysis for interlocking orthotropic interfaces

An assemblage of interlocking blocks can be modelled as a set of rigid units with the potential failure surfaces on their boundaries. The interlocking blocks are rigid units that, on their faces, have locks (projections and depressions) keeping the blocks together and preventing them from sliding, as shown for the sample in [Figure 1a](#). One of the potential failures of such an interlocking block is the cracking of the connections between the locks and the main body of the blocks ([Figure 1b](#)). A lock connection can be cracked due to bending or torsion-shear failures when the lock is subjected to lateral forces. The interlocking blocks can also fail when the frictional resistance of the dry joints between the blocks is violated. In this case the two blocks are displaced with respect to each other along the locks ([Figure 1c](#)). Two interlocking blocks can be separated from each other at the tensionless dry joints as well. Other possible failures can be prevented by considering the main body of the block rigid enough.

Therefore, an interlocking block is herein modelled by assuming two types of failure interface between the rigid main body of the block and the rigid locks (orthotropic interfaces): the dry joints between two individual blocks ([Figure 1d](#), blue strips) and the so-called fracture planes between each lock and the block main body ([Figure 1d](#), red strips).

Figure 1. a) Two interlocking blocks with a shared corrugated interface; b) and c) sliding failures normal and parallel to the locks, respectively; d) two types of failure plane between the main bodies.

The model is simplified by merging the dry joint and the fracture plane of each lock on the same plane. Adopting the Livesley's concave contact method [32, 35], the stress state at the merged failure planes is represented by the internal forces at a number of contact points distributed on the centreline of each lock ([Figure 2](#)). These forces should be in equilibrium with the external forces and moments applied to the block centroid. The internal forces are also limited within the valid ranges to avoid the failures introduced above: the component r^n of the internal force normal to the interface should be in

compression, i.e., have a non-positive value; the component r^{t1} tangential to the interface and parallel to the lock centreline should satisfy the Coulomb's law of friction; and the component r^{t2} tangential to the interface and normal to the lock centreline should satisfy the shear resistance at the contact point. The latter is a portion of the total shear resistance of the lock, which is herein considered to be $T_0 = \tau_k s b$, where s and b are the lock thickness and length, respectively, and τ_k is the masonry shear strength. This portion is assigned by the weight p_i , so that for each lock with l contact points it will be $\sum_{i=1}^l p_i = 1$.

The equilibrium approach of standard limit analysis is then adopted, assuming associated flow rules (friction with dilatancy) for the sliding governed by the Coulomb's law. The limit analysis problem can be written as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \text{objective function:} & \\ \min \frac{1}{2} \|C_{eq} \cdot \vec{r} + \vec{E}\|^2 = 0 & \text{Equilibrium equation} \\ \text{subjected to:} & \\ \vec{r}^n \leq 0 & \text{compression constraint} \\ |\vec{r}^{t1}| \leq \mu |\vec{r}^n| & \text{friction constraint} \\ |\vec{r}^{t2}| \leq \vec{p} T_0. & \text{shear constraint} \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

where C_{eq} is the equilibrium coefficient matrix, \vec{r}^n , \vec{r}^{t1} , \vec{r}^{t2} , and \vec{r} are the vectors of the normal components, tangential components along the locks, tangential components parallel to the locks, and all the normal and tangential components of the internal forces, respectively. Moreover, \vec{p} is the vector of weights related to shear resistance at the contact points and \vec{E} is the vector of all external forces and moments.

Several options for the contact point distribution and also for the allocation of portions of the lock shear resistance to each point has been tested and reported in a previous work [26]. It has been observed that the two options depicted in Figure 2 have the best agreement with the actual shear-torsion resistance of the blocks and the convex contact model [36].

Figure 2. Internal forces on the contact points; two options for the contact point distribution and shear resistance definition representing the interface actual torsion-shear resistance.

However, distributing the contact points on the lock centreline can result in the false estimation of the bending capacity of an interface in the plane normal to the lock interfaces so that the estimated value is less than the actual bending resistance of the interface. Concave contact model, classically, considers the contact points at the corners of an interface. When one point is in compression and the

other one in tension, bending failure occurs and the block starts to rotate about the point in compression.

In this work, lock centrelines are not located on the block interface edges and this reduces the bending capacity of the model. It could be modified by assigning to the compression constraint the coefficients that are related to the distance between the contact points and the interface edges. However, this is out of scope of this paper, which, instead, remedies the situation by considering the contact points on the centreline endpoints (option 2 in Figure 2) and also by increasing the number of locks, making the lock centrelines closer to the interface edges.

2.1. Implementation

The concave contact method extended to the interlocking interfaces is herein formulated for the single layer assemblages whose blocks are propagated along two local U and V directions, modelling stack bond pattern (Figure 3a). The block faces are classified in four 2-dimensional arrays, including the shell extrados $uv0$, intrados $uv1$, and interfaces along U (uw) and V (vw) directions. Assigning the number and orientation of the locks, block faces of each set can be modelled as in Figure 3b.

Figure 3. An assemblage with interlocking uw interfaces. a) Exploded view of the block faces classified in four 2-dimensional arrays and b) local coordinate systems on the faces of a block.

The block faces located on the outer surfaces of the shell can be selected as the supports of the assemblage. An external force and torque are applied to each block centroid. The equilibrium equation for a hexahedron block is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix}
e_1^{nx} & e_1^{t1x} & e_1^{t2x} & \dots & e_1^{nx} & e_1^{t1x} & e_1^{t2x} & \dots & e_8^{nx} & e_8^{t1x} & e_8^{t2x} & \dots & e_8^{nx} & e_8^{t1x} & e_8^{t2x} \\
e_1^{ny} & e_1^{t1y} & e_1^{t2y} & \dots & e_1^{ny} & e_1^{t1y} & e_1^{t2y} & \dots & e_8^{ny} & e_8^{t1y} & e_8^{t2y} & \dots & e_8^{ny} & e_8^{t1y} & e_8^{t2y} \\
e_1^{nz} & e_1^{t1z} & e_1^{t2z} & \dots & e_1^{nz} & e_1^{t1z} & e_1^{t2z} & \dots & e_8^{nz} & e_8^{t1z} & e_8^{t2z} & \dots & e_8^{nz} & e_8^{t1z} & e_8^{t2z} \\
\overline{e_1^n} \times \overline{d_{1,1}}^x & \overline{e_1^{t1}} \times \overline{d_{1,1}}^x & \overline{e_1^{t2}} \times \overline{d_{1,1}}^x & \dots & \overline{e_1^n} \times \overline{d_{m,1}}^x & \overline{e_1^{t1}} \times \overline{d_{m,1}}^x & \overline{e_1^{t2}} \times \overline{d_{m,1}}^x & \dots & \overline{e_8^n} \times \overline{d_{1,8}}^x & \overline{e_8^{t1}} \times \overline{d_{1,8}}^x & \overline{e_8^{t2}} \times \overline{d_{1,8}}^x & \dots & \overline{e_8^n} \times \overline{d_{n,8}}^x & \overline{e_8^{t1}} \times \overline{d_{n,8}}^x & \overline{e_8^{t2}} \times \overline{d_{n,8}}^x \\
\overline{e_1^n} \times \overline{d_{1,1}}^y & \overline{e_1^{t1}} \times \overline{d_{1,1}}^y & \overline{e_1^{t2}} \times \overline{d_{1,1}}^y & \dots & \overline{e_1^n} \times \overline{d_{m,1}}^y & \overline{e_1^{t1}} \times \overline{d_{m,1}}^y & \overline{e_1^{t2}} \times \overline{d_{m,1}}^y & \dots & \overline{e_8^n} \times \overline{d_{1,8}}^y & \overline{e_8^{t1}} \times \overline{d_{1,8}}^y & \overline{e_8^{t2}} \times \overline{d_{1,8}}^y & \dots & \overline{e_8^n} \times \overline{d_{n,8}}^y & \overline{e_8^{t1}} \times \overline{d_{n,8}}^y & \overline{e_8^{t2}} \times \overline{d_{n,8}}^y \\
\overline{e_1^n} \times \overline{d_{1,1}}^z & \overline{e_1^{t1}} \times \overline{d_{1,1}}^z & \overline{e_1^{t2}} \times \overline{d_{1,1}}^z & \dots & \overline{e_1^n} \times \overline{d_{m,1}}^z & \overline{e_1^{t1}} \times \overline{d_{m,1}}^z & \overline{e_1^{t2}} \times \overline{d_{m,1}}^z & \dots & \overline{e_8^n} \times \overline{d_{1,8}}^z & \overline{e_8^{t1}} \times \overline{d_{1,8}}^z & \overline{e_8^{t2}} \times \overline{d_{1,8}}^z & \dots & \overline{e_8^n} \times \overline{d_{n,8}}^z & \overline{e_8^{t1}} \times \overline{d_{n,8}}^z & \overline{e_8^{t2}} \times \overline{d_{n,8}}^z
\end{bmatrix}
\begin{bmatrix}
r_{1,1}^n \\
r_{1,1}^{t1} \\
r_{1,1}^{t2} \\
\vdots \\
r_{m,1}^n \\
r_{m,1}^{t1} \\
r_{m,1}^{t2} \\
\vdots \\
r_{n,8}^n \\
r_{n,8}^{t1} \\
r_{n,8}^{t2} \\
\vdots \\
r_{n,8}^n \\
r_{n,8}^{t1} \\
r_{n,8}^{t2}
\end{bmatrix}
=
\begin{bmatrix}
EF^x \\
EF^y \\
EF^z \\
ET^x \\
ET^y \\
ET^z
\end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where interfaces 1 and 8 has m and n contact points. Rows 1 to 3 of the coefficient matrix are arranged to cancel out the external forces EF in x , y , and z directions while Rows 4 to 6 are arranged to cancel out the external torques ET in x , y , and z directions. Moreover, $\overline{e_j^n}$, $\overline{e_j^{t1}}$, and $\overline{e_j^{t2}}$ are the unit vectors of the axes of the local coordinates at interface j (Figure 3b); $\overline{d_{i,k}}$ is the relative position of the control point i on the interface j and $\overline{d_{i,k}^n}$, $\overline{d_{i,k}^{t1}}$, $\overline{d_{i,k}^{t2}}$ are their components along the axes of the local coordinates for interface j .

Arranging all the block faces of a single layer assemblage, with p blocks in the U direction and q blocks in the V direction, in an array by flattening four 2-dimensional arrays of the block faces and then concatenating them, Eq. (2) can be rewritten as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix}
uv0_{1,1} & uv0_{1,2} \dots uv0_{q,p} & uv1_{1,1} & uv1_{1,2} \dots uv1_{q,p} & uw_{1,1} & uw_{1,2} & \dots & uw_{q+1,p} & vw_{1,1} & vw_{2,1} & \dots & vw_{q,p+1} \\
\hline
[C_{uv0_{1,1}} & | & C_{uv1_{1,1}} & | & C_{uw_{1,1}} & C_{uw_{1,2}} & | & C_{vw_{1,1}} & C_{vw_{2,1}} & | & \dots & R_{uv0_{1,1}} \\
\vdots & & & & & & & & & & & \vdots \\
R_{uv0_{q,p}} & & & & & & & & & & & R_{uv1_{1,1}} \\
\vdots & & & & & & & & & & & \vdots \\
R_{uv1_{q,p}} & & & & & & & & & & & R_{uw_{1,1}} \\
\vdots & & & & & & & & & & & \vdots \\
R_{uw_{q+1,p}} & & & & & & & & & & & R_{vw_{1,1}} \\
\vdots & & & & & & & & & & & \vdots \\
R_{vw_{q,p+1}} & & & & & & & & & & & R_{vw_{q,p+1}}
\end{bmatrix} = E \quad (3)$$

An individual interface enumerated as i^{th} in the U direction and j^{th} in the V direction is denoted by subscript $i;j$. Then, R with the subscript showing the block face number includes the internal forces at all the control points on the interface.

Eq. (3) can be specified for two blocks with one shared interface so that the internal forces on the two block faces making the shared interface have the same value but in the opposite directions. This equation can be expressed as:

$$\left[\begin{array}{c|c|c|c|c} C_{uv0_{1;1}}^{B1;1} & C_{uv1_{1;1}}^{B1;1} & C_{uw1_{1;1}}^{B1;1} & C_{uw1_{1;2}}^{B1;1} & C_{vw1_{1;1}}^{B1;1} \\ & C_{uv0_{1;2}}^{B1;2} & C_{uv1_{1;1}}^{B1;2} & C_{uw1_{1;2}}^{B1;2} & C_{vw1_{1;2}}^{B1;2} \\ & & C_{uv1_{1;1}}^{B1;2} & C_{uw1_{1;2}}^{B1;2} & C_{vw1_{1;2}}^{B1;2} \\ & & & C_{uw1_{1;3}}^{B1;2} & \\ & & & & C_{vw2_{1;1}}^{B1;1} \\ & & & & C_{vw2_{2;1}}^{B1;2} \end{array} \right] \begin{bmatrix} R_{uv0_{1;1}} \\ \vdots \\ R_{uv0_{q;p}} \\ R_{uv1_{1;1}} \\ \vdots \\ R_{uv1_{q;p}} \\ R_{uw1_{1;1}} \\ \vdots \\ R_{uw_{q+1;p}} \\ R_{vw1_{1;1}} \\ \vdots \\ R_{vw_{q;p+1}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} E^{B1;1} \\ E^{B1;2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where an individual block enumerated as i^{th} in the U direction and j^{th} in the V direction is denoted by the superscript $B_i;j$.

The overall equilibrium equation can be constructed by adding the equilibrium equations of the other blocks to Eq. (4). The equilibrium equation is constrained by three linear inequalities: compression, frictional and shear constraints as presented in Eq. (1).

The formulation can be extended to the closed surfaces, in the U and/or V directions by adding a linear equality constraint, which keeps similar the value of the internal forces on the block faces at which the surface is closed (Figure 4b, red line), but with opposite directions.

Figure 4. a) Open and b) closed surfaces demonstrating different ways to arrange the blocks on a surface.

Finally, the limit analysis is carried out by solving the equilibrium linear equation (the complete form of Eq. (4) including all the blocks) under the linear compression, frictional and shear inequalities. The formulated method has been implemented to develop a plug-in within the grasshopper (GH) editor, using C# language. The digital process including the modelling of the overall shell and its blocks as well as the interlocking interfaces are carried out in the grasshopper editor.

A GH component has been developed, whose inputs are the geometric data of the modelled assemblage, together with the assigned friction coefficient, shear strength and loading and boundary conditions. Given these data, the coefficient matrices and the right-hand side vectors of the equilibrium equation and the compression, frictional and shear inequalities are built in the C# framework. The linear problem is solved by least square optimization using MATLAB as backend. For the optimization MATLAB's lsqin method is used. The output of the GH component is the optimization solution which represents the internal forces of the structurally feasible model.

2.2. Validation

The proposed concave contact method for the interlocking interfaces is validated using three examples: a semi-circular arch, a hemispherical dome and a pavilion vault. The validation is first based on the comparison of the thinnest structurally feasible systems composed of conventional blocks for the examples obtained using the developed plug-in with the results reported in the literature, for different friction coefficients. Then, the thinnest structurally feasible systems composed of interlocking blocks are obtained for different lock orientations. It is expected that the optimal interlocking model with large values of shear strength is thinner than the optimal model with the conventional blocks, for the same friction coefficient.

2.2.1. Semi-circular arch

A semi-circular arch with 10 m centreline radius and 1 m depth is modelled as an assemblage of 40 blocks under their own weight, with 1 N/m³ density. Assuming conventional block interfaces, [Figure 5](#) shows the relation between the minimum thickness of the arch and the friction coefficient, obtained by the developed plug-in. It can be observed that the obtained results are in a very good agreement with the results reported by Gilbert et al. [34] Casapulla et al. [25].

Figure 5. The thinnest semi-circular arch with conventional block interfaces for different friction coefficients, obtained by the proposed method and other methods existing in the literature.

In all the three curves of [Figure 5](#), the minimum thickness depends on the friction coefficient between two small values (e.g., for the proposed method, between 0.33 and 0.4). This shows that in the limit state, the sliding failure occurs due to the small sliding resistance at interfaces. To increase the interface sliding resistance, interlocking blocks with large shear strength can be used.

Considering interlocking interfaces, [Figure 6](#) shows the relation between the minimum arch thickness and the friction coefficient, for different lock orientations. As expected, when the locks are parallel to the arch plane (lock orientation equal to $\pi/2$ rad), the results are identical to those obtained for the arch with conventional interfaces. Changing the lock orientation from $\pi/2$ to 0 rad, the minimum arch thickness reduces for the same amount of friction coefficient. Finally, when the locks are normal to the arch plane (lock orientation equal to 0 rad), the sliding resistance is only governed by the interface shear resistance. Therefore, the minimum arch thickness does not increase by reducing the friction coefficient, showing that sliding failure never happens.

Figure 6. The thinnest semi-circular arch with interlocking blocks for the lock orientations ranging from 0 to $\pi/2$ rad.

2.2.2. Hemispherical dome

A hemispherical dome with 10 m centreline radius is modelled in this section. It is composed of 20 rows and 40 blocks at each row under their own weight, with 1 N/m³ density. Assuming conventional interfaces, Figure 7 shows the relation between the minimum dome thickness and the friction coefficient, provided by the developed plug-in and compared with the results obtained by Simon and Bagi [37] and Hyman [7]. Since no tensile hoop stresses are considered in the model with stack bond pattern, a good agreement between the results obtained by the proposed method and by Hyman's cracked model [7] can be observed. By analogy with the semi-circular arch, the minimum thickness increases when the friction coefficient decreases within the range between two small values (e.g., for the proposed method, between 0.2 and 0.23).

Using interlocking interfaces with large shear strength, the sliding resistance at interfaces increases and, therefore, the dome minimum thickness decreases, keeping fixed the value of the friction coefficient. Figure 8 demonstrates the relation between the minimum thickness of the dome with interlocking interfaces and the friction coefficient for different lock orientations. As expected, the result obtained for the lock orientation equal to $\pi/2$ rad (radial locks) is the closest to the results obtained for conventional blocks. As was observed for the semi-circular arch, when the lock orientation changes from $\pi/2$ to 0 rad, the minimum dome thickness reduces for the same amount of friction coefficient. And ultimately, the lock orientation equal to 0 rad (parallel locks), increases the sliding resistance enough so that no sliding failure occurs in the dome.

Figure 7. The thinnest hemispherical dome with conventional block interfaces for different friction coefficients, provided by the proposed method and other methods existing in the literature.

Figure 8. The thinnest hemispherical dome with interlocking blocks for the lock orientations ranging from 0 to $\pi/2$ rad.

2.2.3. Pavilion vault

A pavilion vault is modelled with 3 m generatrix radius, spanning a 6 m by 6 m square (Figure 9). It is composed of 20 rows and 32 blocks at each row under their own weight, with 1 N/m³ density. Figure 10 shows the relation between the minimum thickness of the vault with conventional interfaces and the friction coefficient, obtained by the developed plug-in and the results reported by D'Ayala and Tomasoni in [38].

Figure 9. The geometric parameters of the chosen pavilion vault [38].

The minimum thickness obtained by the developed plug-in is independent of friction coefficients larger than 0.6 and a similar condition was observed by D'Ayala and Tomasoni [38] for friction coefficients larger than 0.5. This shows that no sliding failure occurs in the assemblage in these conditions. As shown in Figure 10, the minimum thickness obtained by the developed plug-in in these conditions is smaller than the one obtained by the cited work.

Instead, when the friction coefficient is between 0.43 and 0.5, the minimum thickness is dependent on it, showing that the sliding failure occurs at the limit state. Within this range, a good agreement between the two graphs obtained by the proposed method and D'Ayala and Tomasoni [38] can be observed. However, unlike the cited method [38], the plug-in finds no valid solution for friction coefficients less than 0.43.

Figure 10. The thinnest pavilion vault with conventional block interfaces for different friction coefficients, obtained by the proposed method and D'Ayala and Tomasoni [38].

Considering interlocking interfaces, Figure 11 shows the relation between the minimum thickness of the vault and the friction coefficient, for different lock orientations. It can be observed that interlocking blocks with any lock orientation decreases the minimum thickness of the vault comparing to conventional blocks. As anticipated, changing the lock orientation from $\pi/2$ to 0 rad (radial to parallel locks), the interface sliding resistance increases and this reduces the minimum thickness of the vault for the same amount of the friction coefficient.

Figure 11. The thinnest pavilion vault with interlocking blocks for the lock orientations ranging from 0 to $\pi/2$ rad.

3. Infeasibility measurement

Whiting et al. [10] proposed a method to measure the structural infeasibility due to the existence of tensile stresses in the model. That work reformulated the limit analysis problem as follows. First, the constraint limiting the normal forces to be in compression was removed, i.e., the normal forces can take any tensile or compressive value. Then, an optimization problem was developed to find the minimum tensile stresses (objective function) while the solution was limited to be equilibrated and satisfying the sliding constraint. Finally, the measure of infeasibility was defined to be the value of the objective function for the optimal solution with the minimum tensile forces.

A similar approach is adopted in this section to measure the structural infeasibility due to the violation of the sliding constraints at the interlocking interfaces. This means that the tangential forces can have any value and the optimization problem is formulated to find the optimal solution with the minimum

tangential forces outside the valid sliding ranges. These forces are defined by the frictional and shear constraints expressed by Eq. (1). The optimal solution is also constrained to be equilibrated, and all the normal forces of the assemblage to be in compression.

To formulate this optimization problem, first an objective function is developed to minimize the tangential forces which are outside the valid sliding ranges (frictional and shear constraints). To this aim, each tangential force r^t (which can be parallel r^{t1} or normal r^{t2} to the locks) is decomposed into two new variables r^{ta} and r^{tb} , so that r^{t1a} and r^{t1b} are parallel and r^{t2a} and r^{t2b} are normal to the locks. In particular, r^{t1a} and r^{t2a} are constrained to satisfy the frictional and shear constraints, respectively, while r^{t1b} and r^{t2b} can take any arbitrary value. Therefore, $r^{t1} = r^{t1a} + r^{t1b}$ and $r^{t2} = r^{t2a} + r^{t2b}$ can also take any value. The objective function tries to minimize r^{t1b} and r^{t2b} by which r^{t1} and r^{t2} get close to the valid sliding ranges, maximally.

The optimization problem has also four constraints: the equilibrium and compressive constraints, and two constraints imposing r^{t1a} and r^{t2a} to respect the frictional and shear criteria, respectively. This problem tries to make r^{t1} and r^{t2} as close as possible to the valid frictional and shear ranges.

Thus, introducing k as a natural number and L as the number of the contact points, the optimization problem including a non-linear objective function and four linear constraints is formulated as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{objective function:} \\ \min \sum_{i=1}^L [(r^{t1b})^{2k} + (r^{t2b})^{2k}] \quad k \in \mathbb{N} \\ \text{subjected to:} \\ C_{eq} \cdot \vec{r} + \vec{E} = 0 \quad \text{Equilibrium equation} \\ \vec{r}^n \leq 0 \quad \text{compression constraint} \\ |\vec{r}^{t1a}| \leq \mu |\vec{r}^n| \quad \text{friction constraint} \\ |\vec{r}^{t2a}| \leq \vec{p} T_0. \quad \text{shear constraint} \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

The value of the objective function for the obtained optimal solution is considered as the measure of infeasibility. Changing the lock geometric parameters, the designer can observe how much the measured infeasibility is decreased or increased.

3.1. Implementation

The mathematical problem formulated for the structural feasibility analysis of the single layer shells in Section 2.1 is herein updated to quantify the infeasibility. The main goal is to replace every individual tangential force r^t by its two components r^{ta} and r^{tb} in the formulations. To this aim, the vector of variables for a hexahedron block in Eq. (2) is extended as follows:

$$\vec{r}^T = [r_{1,1}^n \ r_{1,1}^{t1a} \ r_{1,1}^{t1b} \ r_{1,1}^{t2a} \ r_{1,1}^{t2b} \ \dots \ r_{n,8}^n \ r_{n,8}^{t1a} \ r_{n,8}^{t1b} \ r_{n,8}^{t2a} \ r_{n,8}^{t2b}] \quad (6)$$

The objective function of Eq. (5) can be written as follows:

$$[0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ \dots \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1] \cdot \vec{r} \cdot \vec{r}^T \quad (7)$$

in which k of Eq. (5) is considered to be 1.

By analogy with Eq. (2), the equilibrium equation for a single block with eight interlocking interfaces, defined in Eq. (5) as an optimization constraint, is expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix}
e_1^{nx} & e_1^{t1x} & e_1^{t1x} & e_1^{t2x} & e_1^{t2x} & \dots & e_1^{nx} & e_1^{t1x} & e_1^{t1x} & e_1^{t2x} & e_1^{t2x} \\
e_1^{ny} & e_1^{t1y} & e_1^{t1y} & e_1^{t2y} & e_1^{t2y} & & e_1^{ny} & e_1^{t1y} & e_1^{t1y} & e_1^{t2y} & e_1^{t2y} \\
e_1^{nz} & e_1^{t1z} & e_1^{t1z} & e_1^{t2z} & e_1^{t2z} & & e_1^{nz} & e_1^{t1z} & e_1^{t1z} & e_1^{t2z} & e_1^{t2z} \\
\overrightarrow{(e_1^n \times d_{1,1})^x} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t1} \times d_{1,1})^x} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t1} \times d_{1,1})^x} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t2} \times d_{1,1})^x} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t2} \times d_{1,1})^x} & & \overrightarrow{(e_1^n \times d_{m,1})^x} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t1} \times d_{m,1})^x} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t1} \times d_{m,1})^x} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t2} \times d_{m,1})^x} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t2} \times d_{m,1})^x} & \dots \\
\overrightarrow{(e_1^n \times d_{1,1})^y} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t1} \times d_{1,1})^y} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t1} \times d_{1,1})^y} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t2} \times d_{1,1})^y} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t2} \times d_{1,1})^y} & & \overrightarrow{(e_1^n \times d_{m,1})^y} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t1} \times d_{m,1})^y} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t1} \times d_{m,1})^y} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t2} \times d_{m,1})^y} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t2} \times d_{m,1})^y} \\
\overrightarrow{(e_1^n \times d_{1,1})^z} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t1} \times d_{1,1})^z} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t1} \times d_{1,1})^z} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t2} \times d_{1,1})^z} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t2} \times d_{1,1})^z} & & \overrightarrow{(e_1^n \times d_{m,1})^z} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t1} \times d_{m,1})^z} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t1} \times d_{m,1})^z} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t2} \times d_{m,1})^z} & \overrightarrow{(e_1^{t2} \times d_{m,1})^z} \\
\vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots
\end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{1,1}^n \\ r_{1,1}^{t1a} \\ r_{1,1}^{t1b} \\ r_{1,1}^{t2a} \\ r_{1,1}^{t2b} \\ \vdots \\ r_{m,1}^n \\ r_{m,1}^{t1a} \\ r_{m,1}^{t1b} \\ r_{m,1}^{t2a} \\ r_{m,1}^{t2b} \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} EF^x \\ EF^y \\ EF^z \\ ET^x \\ ET^y \\ ET^z \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

while the updated vector of variables in Eq. (6) is used to develop the three other constraints of Eq. (5), limiting the normal forces to be in compression and r^{t1a} and r^{t2a} to be in the valid frictional and shear ranges, respectively.

The updated formulation is implemented to construct a GH component for the infeasibility measurement within the plug-in introduced in Section 2. To solve the quadratic programming, MATLAB's `fmincon` is used. The interior point optimization is chosen to reduce the run time, making the plug-in suitable for the early stage shape exploration.

3.2. Validation

To validate the proposed infeasibility measurement method, the three examples analysed in Section 2.2 (the semi-circular arch, the hemispherical dome, and the pavilion vault), are used. The geometric parameters of the examples are as explained in Section 2.2. The thickness of the semi-circular arch, the hemispherical dome, and the pavilion vault are chosen to be 1.06, 0.44, and 0.12 m, respectively. The selected thicknesses are the minimum thicknesses of the examples when the large friction coefficients are exerted. As can be observed in Figures 5, 7, and 10, the assemblages with the chosen thicknesses, when composed of conventional blocks, are structurally feasible for the large friction coefficients and infeasible for the small friction coefficients. Similarly, from Figures 6, 8, and 11 it can be derived that the assemblages with the chosen thicknesses, when composed of interlocking blocks, are structurally feasible for the lock orientations producing large sliding resistances and infeasible for the lock orientations producing small sliding resistances.

Tables 1, 3, and 5 present the measure of infeasibility of the semi-circular arch, hemispherical dome and pavilion vault, respectively, for different lock orientations. Each table reports the infeasibility measure for a low (first row) and a large (third row) friction coefficient. The second and fourth rows of each table simply report the feasibility of the assemblage for the chosen friction coefficients, using the extended limit analysis presented in Section 2. The results reported in the second and fourth rows can also be observed in Figures 6, 8, and 11 as well.

As demonstrated in Table 1, the structural infeasibilities of the models were measured relatively acceptable, for the low friction coefficient equal to 0.33. As expected, the infeasibility reduces towards zero when the lock orientation changes from $\pi/2$ towards 0 rad. Models with the infeasibility measure less than 0.10882 are recognized feasible by the extended limit analysis. For the large friction coefficient taken as 10, the infeasibility measures are very close to zero for all the lock orientations, showing that all the models are structurally valid.

Table 1. Measure of infeasibility for the semi-circular arch; f and i stand for feasibility and infeasibility of a model, respectively.

	$\mu \backslash$ orientation (rad)	0	0.3	0.6	0.9	1.2	1.57
infeasibility measure	0.33	0.026	0.044	0.064	0.084	0.108	0.157
limit analysis	0.33	f	f	f	f	i	i
infeasibility measure	10	4×10^{-4}	9×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}	0.002	0.007	0.011
limit analysis	10	f	f	f	f	f	f

As shown in Table 2, for the low friction coefficient equal to 0.2, the measured infeasibility reduces towards zero when the lock orientation changes from 0 to $\pi/2$ rad. Models with the infeasibility measure less than 0.051404 are recognized feasible by the extended limit analysis. This shows that the infeasibility measurement method performs better to distinguish the invalid hemispherical domes when compared to the semi-circular arches, given that the infeasibility measure of a structurally valid model should ideally be zero. For the large friction coefficient, the measure of infeasibility is quite close to zero for all the lock orientations, showing that all the models are structurally feasible.

Table 2. Measure of infeasibility for the hemispherical dome; f and i stand for feasibility and infeasibility of a model, respectively.

	$\mu \backslash$ orientation (rad)	0	0.3	0.6	0.9	1.2	1.57
infeasibility measure	0.2	0.002	0.010	0.022	0.036	0.051	0.071
limit analysis	0.2	f	f	f	f	i	i
infeasibility measure	10	3×10^{-5}	3×10^{-4}	9×10^{-4}	0.002	0.003	0.007
limit analysis	10	f	f	f	f	f	f

Table 3 can measure the infeasibility of the models with zero friction coefficient satisfactorily, where the measured infeasibilities of all the invalid models are more than 0.184 while the measured infeasibilities of all the structurally valid models with the large friction coefficient are very close to zero.

The measured infeasibility for the pavilion vault when $\mu = 0$, however, has slight deviation from the expectations. The infeasibility reduces when the lock orientation is changed from 0 to $\pi/2$. Yet, unexpectedly, this measure increases when the lock orientation changes from 1.2 to 0.6 Rad. The reason lies in the facts that the chosen solver is not able to reach the global minima properly. In fact, MATLAB's fmincon tries to minimize the objective function, yet the equilibrium and other limiting constraints are not fully satisfied.

As a future work, the plug-in will be extended to automatically adjust the lock orientation of an infeasible assemblage to minimize the measured infeasibility. Therefore, the anomaly stated above will be remedied to find the optimization path more effectively.

Table 3. Measure of infeasibility for the pavilion vault; f and i stand for feasibility and infeasibility of a model, respectively.

	μ \orientation (rad)	0	0.3	0.6	0.9	1.2	1.57
infeasibility measure	0	0.184	0.285	0.281702	0.258	0.238	0.234
limit analysis	0	i	i	i	i	i	i
infeasibility measure	10	0.003	0.008	0.010	0.011	0.012	0.014
limit analysis	10	f	f	f	f	f	f

4. Results

In addition to the three classical models analysed in [Sections 2 and 3](#), the validation of the proposed methods is herein completed with three more examples. These were already analysed in a previous work [28], where the extended limit analysis was validated and the influence of several parameters (orientation of the locks, friction coefficient, concave model option) on the sliding resistance was investigated. In this section, these examples are used to validate the novel infeasibility measurement method and to demonstrate the capability of the plug-in to model complex shapes under different loading conditions.

4.1. Example 1

An assemblage of three blocks under their own weight, represented in [Figure 12a](#), is modelled. Two left and right-side block faces are considered to be the supports of the structure, while the interlocking interfaces are depicted in yellow in the figure. The assigned material density, friction coefficient and shear strength are 1 N/m^3 , 0, and 1 N/m^2 , respectively. The graph in [Figure 12b](#) demonstrates the infeasibility measure for different lock orientations. As expected, the minimum and maximum infeasibility measures are registered for the assemblage with the horizontal (lock orientation = 0 rad) and vertical (lock orientation = $\pi/2$ rad) locks, respectively.

[Figure 13](#) reports the stress states for the different lock orientations found by solving the infeasibility measure optimization problem.

(a)

(b)

Figure 12. a) Example 1 with dimensions in meters, b) the measured infeasibility for the lock orientation ranging from 0 to $\pi/2$ rad.

Figure 13. Stress states found by the infeasibility measurement method.

4.2. Example 2

The second example consists of an assemblage of eight blocks sketched in Figure 14a, where each individual block is subjected to its own weight and a radial force outward. The value of both external forces applied to a block is the same. The structure transfers the external forces to the ground through the bottom block faces and the interlocking interfaces are shown in yellow in the figure. Same as Example 1, the assigned material density, friction coefficient and shear strength are 1 N/m^3 , 0, and 1 N/m^2 , respectively.

The infeasibility measures for different lock orientations are reported in the graph of Figure 14b. The graph clearly shows that finding the minimum value of the infeasibility measure by adjusting the lock orientation is a challenging task due to the existence of the local minima. Figure 15 collects the stress states obtained by solving the infeasibility measure optimization problem, for different lock orientations.

(a)

(b)

Figure 14. a) Example 2 with dimensions in meters, b) the measured infeasibility for the lock orientation ranging from 0 to $\pi/2$ rad.

Figure 15. Stress states found by the infeasibility measurement method.

4.3. Example 3

The last example is a double curvature vault with 4.6 m length and width, 2 m height, and 0.15 m thickness (Figure 16). The assemblage is under its own weight and supported by four blocks at the assemblage corners. Same as Examples 1 and 2, the assigned material density, friction coefficient and shear strength are 1 N/m^3 , 0, and 1 N/m^2 , respectively. The measure of infeasibility is found for three options: 1) an assemblage with conventional blocks (Figure 16a); 2) an assemblage with the interlocking interfaces only in one direction (depicted in red within Figure 16b) and 3) an assemblage with all interlocking interfaces (depicted in red and yellow in Figure 16c). As expected, the largest and lowest infeasibility measures belong to the first and third options, respectively.

Figure 16. Example 3. Measured infeasibility and the stress states found by the infeasibility measurement method for the assemblage with a) conventional blocks, b) interlocking interface in one direction and c) interlocking interface in two directions.

5. Conclusions

This paper presented a digital framework to design the structurally feasible assemblages composed of interlocking blocks with corrugated interfaces having orthotropic sliding behaviour. First, the extended limit analysis to the orthotropic interlocking interfaces was validated using some examples with different lock orientations. Then, the limit analysis was reformulated to develop an optimization problem to measure the infeasibility of a model. This allows the designers to tune the geometric parameters of the interlocking blocks to reduce the quantified infeasibility. This non-linear optimization problem tries to find the optimal solution keeping the tangential forces maximally close to the valid sliding ranges, defined by the frictional and shear constraints, while the model is in equilibrium and the normal forces are all in compression.

Both the extended limit analysis and the infeasibility measurement method were implemented to develop a plug-in for Grasshopper to design single layer shells with arbitrary geometries. The extended limit analysis and the infeasibility measurement method were validated through several examples compared with the results available in the literature. Furthermore, examples with different shapes and loading conditions were provided to demonstrate the performance of the plug-in. The drawbacks of the extended limit analysis to estimate the bending capacity of the assemblage, as well as the limitation of the infeasibility measurement method to find the global minimum solutions, were also addressed.

In the future work, the mentioned limitations are intended to be solved and an optimization problem will be developed to automatically adjust the interlocking geometric parameters to remove the structural infeasibility.

6. Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement No. 791235. It reflects only the authors' view and the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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